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NANO BIOSENSORS: CURRENT DEVELOPMENTS & USES

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ABSTRACT

Since a long time ago, one of the trendiest topics catching the attention of scientists is biosensing. This is true because biological systems are highly complex and are inextricably linked to the presence of a wholesome environment. Significant changes have also recently been made to the design of biosensors. Biosensors have gained popularity for a variety of uses, including the assessment of food quality, environmental monitoring, and the identification of clinical and metabolic issues. The field of nanotechnology has introduced several intriguing elements that have the potential to enhance sensing phenomena. Utilizing a variety of nanomaterials, including nanoparticles, nanotubes, nanorods, and nanowires, has greatly improved repeatability and allowed for speedier detection. The assembly of nanomaterial features is what gives rise to the special qualities of nanomaterials, which include strong electrical conductivity, improved shock resistance, sensitive reactions like piezoelectric and adaptable color-based detecting methods. This research focuses on the many kinds of biosensors that are based on various kinds of nanomaterials and discusses their implications and developmental features.

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INTRODUCTION

Better health care delivery depends on higher standards of health care management. These can be attained by making timely judgments based on quick diagnoses, astute data analysis, and informatics analysis. To improve health and wellbeing, this necessitates the use of intelligent therapies, analytical instruments, and diagnostic systems. The optimization of therapies is essential for the effective management of a disease's course and monitoring assessment, which is crucial for understanding epidemics and managing illness. Therefore, it is essential to create intelligent diagnostic systems, such as point-of-care devices, for individualized health care. Point-of-care testing guarantees prompt analyte detection near patients, enabling improved illness diagnosis, tracking, and treatment. Quick medical decisions are also made possible by the early diagnosis of diseases, which improves patient outcomes by allowing patients to begin treatment sooner. Next-generation point-of-care testing is being made possible by the development of several potential point-of-care devices in recent years. Since they are directly in charge of an assay's bioanalytical performance, biosensors—analytical devices that transform or transduce a biological reaction into a quantitative signal are an essential part of point-of-care devices. As seen in Figure 1, the quantifiable signal can be optical, electrochemical, piezoelectric, or thermal. Because of their excellent potential for real-sample analysis and their high sensitivity, precision, and low detection limits, electrochemical biosensors have garnered a lot of attention recently. Since they typically estimate the levels of biological markers or any chemical reaction by producing signals primarily associated with the concentration of an analyte, they have been investigated for their potential point-of-care applications necessary for personalized health care management. As a result, they can detect disease-causing markers, such as bodily fluids. The combination of biosensors and nanotechnology can enhance assessment of the disease start and its progression and aid in the planning of treatment because of their high selectivity and sensitivity, which have enabled early diagnosis and management of targeted diseases.

Figure 1 Typical biosensor with all its components.

Physical, chemical, and biological systems at the 1–100 nanometer scale is produced and used in the field of nanotechnology, which examines the manipulation of matter on the atomic and molecular levels. When compared to their bulk counterparts, these materials usually referred to as nanoparticles or nanomaterials have extraordinary physical, chemical, and biological properties that are revolutionizing science. They have a wide range of applications, particularly in the fields of biomedical, optical, medical imaging, catalysis, and electronics. Their enhanced catalytic qualities, electron transport, and capacity for biomolecule labeling and adsorption make them ideal for biosensing. Because of the distinct physicochemical characteristics of nanoparticles, biosensors such as Nano sensors for point-of-care illness diagnosis have been developed. Because of their compact size, alternative techniques including electrochemical and enzymatic biosensors typically work better because of increased electron transfer rates and shorter enzyme-to-electrode distances. Additionally, localized surface plasmon resonance (SPR) can be improved by noble metal nanoparticles, which in turn can enhance optical biosensors. For instance, the interparticle plasmon interaction that causes these nanoparticles to change color has been extensively utilized in biosensors that rely on the aggregation of nanoparticles. The current trends of these Nano sensors in point-of-care diagnostics are examined in this review.

COMPONENTS OF NANO BIOSENSORS:-

They are made up of three part

- Sensitive biological element:** These can be either living biological materials (for example microorganisms, cell receptors etc.) or biological molecules (for example organelles, enzymes, antibodies, synthetic receptors, nucleic acids etc.)
- The transducer:** It measures the physical change due to the reaction of sensitive biological element with bioreceptor. They work directly or indirectly depending upon which biosensors are classified as:
 - Direct detection biosensors:** The biological reaction can be directly measured. E.g. biosensors using antibodies or cell receptors (i.e. non catalytic ligands).
 - Indirect detection biosensors:** The biological reaction is detected by secondary detector. E.g. labeled antibodies, catalytic enzymes.
- The detector:** Signals from the transducer are amplified, analyzed, converted to concentration units and then stored in storage device.

WORKING PRINCIPLE OF BIOSENSORS

The initial step in the operation of biosensors is the immobilization of a desired biological material, usually an enzyme, using conventional techniques such as physical entrapment, covalent bonding, or non-covalent bonding. This immobile biological entity is strongly associated with the transducer. A biosensor measures the electrical signal that the analyte produces. Rarely, the analyte is converted into a product that could be associated with the release of electrons, heat, gas (such as oxygen), or hydrogen ions. Variations in the product can be converted by the transducer into electrical impulses that can be detected and amplified. In order to develop a biological model that provides data to an automated regulator or a human, a biosensor system combines a variety of different items, such as a regulated group, a biosensor, a replenishing information system, and a data investigation scheme. In order to produce a chemical or physical reaction, the choice of biological components is based on a number of factors, including specificity, storage, environmental stability, and operational consistency. This reaction is converted into a signal by the transducer.[10-13].

Figure 2 The measurement of flow for a biosensor.

Figure 3 Ideal requirement for biosensor-based detection assay.

BASIC CHARACTERISTICS OF BIOSENSORS

Accuracy: There should be minimal to no false positive and false negative outcomes from biosensors.

- Evaluation time: Biosensors should provide a real-time reaction, especially when verifying the authenticity of unpreserved food items.
- Sensitivity: Biosensors' need to identify false negative results reduces their analytical sensitivity.
- Specificity: The biosensor is more effective in distinguishing between the target organism, poison, and novel organism.
- Reproducible: Biosensor tests ought to be highly repeatable and easily calibrable.
- Robust: The biosensor needs to be serializable, able to withstand variations in temperature, ionic strength, and pH.
- Validation: Defying the present conventional procedure, the biosensor assay should be conducted abroad.[10-12]

ADVANTAGES

Quick and ongoing measurement

- Excellent specificity • Reagent may be calibrated using a very small amount.
- Quick reaction times
- Biosensors are classified as follows depending on their mechanism of transduction

THERE ARE 5 TYPES OF BIOSENSORS AS LISTED BELOW

1. Optical Biosensor
 - a) Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) Biosensors
 - b) Piezoelectric Biosensor
2. Resonant Biosensor
3. Thermal Biosensor
4. Ion-selective Biosensor
5. Electrochemical Biosensor
 - a. Potentiometric
 - b. Amperometric
 - c. Impedimetric
 - d. Voltammetric

1. Optical Biosensor

The light source and several optical components that produce a certain type of light beam and guide it toward a mediator, an improved sensor, and a picture detector make up the optical biosensors. Variations in genetic synthesis, green fluorescent protein (GFP), and later auto fluorescent proteins (AFP) The creation of genetically encoded biosensors has been recommended by researchers. It is easy to set up, move, and manipulate this biosensor within cells. It is easy to assemble, transport, and work with this biosensor inside of cells. Two types of optical biosensors can be distinguished. The signal that measures light is measured by the optical biosensor. The biosensor can be constructed by optical diffraction or electrochemiluminescence. The most well-known use for optical transducers is the detection of microorganisms. Small variations in thickness or refractive index appear to be detected by the optical biosensor when cells drag to immobilized receptors on the transducer's surface. Other biosensors provide information on variations in concentration and molecule count to represent variations in light. There are several optical techniques that are discussed for identifying bacteria and other diseases, including resonant mirrors and interferometers, monomode dielectric waveguides, Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR), and so on.

Figure 3 Optical biosensors.

• Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) Biosensors

There is a phenomena known as surface plasmon resonance. Bimolecular interface analysis (BIA) can be used with optical illumination on a metal surface. The most well-known use of it is in oscillation compactness controls near the dielectric constant boundary. The free electron, which is provided by a suitable photon with light energy, is illustrated as plasmons. The width of the ensuing electromagnetic plasmon or evanescent wave is greatest at emerging (ambient) medium. Most likely, the ambient medium is watery and not as compacted. The Plasmon Surface Wave (SPW) is an indication that is broken to a depth of approximately one wavelength by the Eva Scent Welle (ESW), which is typically directed by waves spreading throughout a rest. In contrast, the Eva Scent Wave (ESW), which is typically directed waves in an organization, such as an optical fiber, is at roughly one wavelength.

- **Piezoelectric Biosensors**

The foundation of piezoelectric bio-sensors is the magnitude of variations in a piezoelectric crystal's resonant frequency brought on by mass crystal instability. The study of plasmonics examines how light interacts with metals or metallic nanostructures. Other materials with plasmonic resonance are graphene and other materials where conductive electrons are available. Plasmonics is a technology that combines photonics and electronics. It is used in optical detection of changes in refractive index and chemical structure-related spectra. They are also useful for extracting important data on the identity, concentration, or presence of relevant compounds. A quartz crystal microbalance is the second type of piezoelectric biosensor, while a surface acoustic wave unit is the first kind. Piezoelectric biosensors appear to be affordable, user-friendly, and real-time. It is generally known that the Pz sensor's surface may be coated with a substance that selectively binds. For example, dropping bacterium-specific antibodies into a solution containing bacteria. The bulk of the crystal will decrease as the bacteria attach to the antibodies.

2. Resonant Biosensor

The Resonant Biologic Sensor combines an antibody (bio-element) with an acoustic wave transducer. Because the analyte fragment (or antigen) is attached to the membrane, the membrane's weight varies. The ensuing mass fluctuation causes a change in the transducer's resonance frequency, which is measured.

3. Thermal Biosensor

One of the most crucial characteristics of biological processes—heat production or absorption, which elevates the reactions' medium temperature—is used by thermal biosensors. Thermal biosensors are made by combining temperature sensors with the molecules of the Zed enzyme. A heat reaction happens as the analyte interacts with the enzymes, revealing the analyte's concentration. Essentially, this apparatus is a small calorimeter, equipped with extremely sensitive thermometers that can typically detect temperature variations between 0.0001°C and 0.05°C. Analyte concentrations less than 10 M are detectable by this method. Thermal biosensors are often used for identifying pathogenic microorganisms and pesticides.

4. Ion-selective Biosensor

Semiconductor FETs with an ion-selective surface are used to create ion-selective biosensors. As the semiconductor and ions interact, the electrical surface potential shifts. After that, the potential difference may be estimated.

5. Electrochemical biosensor

There are three different kinds of electrochemical biosensors: conductometric, potentiometric, and amperometric. This focuses on the reference electrode and finds the current that reduced or oxidized species create on the electrode surface. The primary uses of an electrochemical biosensor are the detection of hybridized DNA, glucose levels, and medications that attach to DNA. The electrochemical biosensor may be categorized as A) Amperometric B) Conductometric based on the measurement of electrical properties. C) Measuring potency.

A) Amperometric

Biosensors with an amperometric response have a high sensitivity for identifying electroactive organisms. Since biological models are not necessarily electrical by nature, enzymes are used to catalyze the creation of radioactive creatures. The element in question is the amperometric element of a biosensor.

B) Conductometric

Through the use of ions or electrons, the conductometric reaction modifies the solution's total resistivity or conductivity, resulting in an electrochemical reaction. Measurements of conductance are somewhat less sensitive. An electric field produced by sinusoidal voltage (AC) aids in reducing undesirable phenomena such as double-layer charging, faradaic processes, and polarization concentration. It entails measuring variables like the solution's resistance and electric conductivity.

C) Potentiometric

A potentiometric biosensor measures the reduction and oxidation potential of an electrochemical process. A potential biosensor works on the basis of the hypothesis that an electrode in a solution experiences an electrochemical reaction that results in a current flow when a gradient voltage is applied to it. The response and reaction class are determined by the voltage at which these reactions take place.

WORKING OF BIOSENSOR

Typically, the transducer produces a modest electric signal that is superimposed over a high, noisy signal that also comprises a high frequency signal that appears casual on the surface or formed inside the electrical components of the transducer baseline. The electrical signal is produced by the transducer, and since it loses its biocatalyst membrane, amplifies the ensuing signal transition, filters, and smoothes, it is common to infer the return of the standard signal from the sample signal. The analogue signal created in this step is sent straight to a display device or stored data. But typically, it is transformed into a digital sign and sent to a microchip stage, where information is altered and stored in a desired format. The most often employed organic element, an enzyme is a large protein fragment that acts as a catalyst for a chemical process, yet it stays intact at the end.

An enzyme reacts with a substrate to build a composite particle that, in the right circumstances, forms a composite molecule that, in the right circumstances, makes the necessary product molecule, unleashing the enzyme when the reaction is finished.

APPLICATIONS OF BIOSENSORS IN PHARMACEUTICAL SECTOR

These days, biosensors are widely used in many industries, including the food industry, medical area, marine zone, and so on. Biosensors outperform traditional methods in terms of strength and sensitivity. Among the advantages of biosensors are their low cost, compact size, easy handling, speed, and more sensitivity and selectivity than current mechanisms. Biosensors are useful for a variety of clinical research and general healthcare tasks. An example that is widely recognized is the glucose oxidase biosensor that a diabetic uses to monitor blood sugar levels. Biosensors are soon to be used in environmental pollution control, industrial treatment and monitoring, and the food and agricultural industries.

BIOSENSORS USE IN DRUG DISCOVERY SECONDARY SCREENING

The primary source of discovery in the fields of antibody description and interface studies for superior biomolecules with comparatively low molecular-like chemicals has always been the biosensor strength found in pharmaceutical items. Biosensors are still relevant, as demonstrated by recent advancements in pharmaceutical research. One tool that has been utilized to identify possible antibody therapy with better affinity and efficacy is the Biacore A100. This relatively new device in the base range will watch a board of directors and four antigenic planes' monoclonal antibody purification simultaneously. The quantity of small molecular weight-like molecules that can be found in the case of immobilized treatment objectives without the required labelling has increased due to the friendliness of a few optical bio-sensors; these molecules are typically 400–500 da in size.¹⁹ A large piece of protein serving as a catalyst for a chemical reaction is the enzyme, which is the most commonly used organic element, but remains unchanged at the end.

BIOSENSORS AS A TOOL FOR BIOPHARMACEUTICAL MANUFACTURING

Candidate molecules for disease targets with a high enough binding attraction are urgently needed to be translated into lower drug doses to achieve a stable and adequate dose schedule for patients. Improved cell lines, improved purification/fermentation for manufacturing effectiveness, increased scalability from the research lab to the production scale, capacity concerns demonstrate, stability formulation, release testing of too harsh safety quality standards, and the efficiency of preclinical testing for safety are just a few of the major issues that had been encountered before. As a result, new and new technologies are used by the industry to address such challenges, and biosensors can contribute to some of these goals. A broad range of biosensors with the most widely employed biosensors based on optical plasmine resonance surface (SPR) concepts are currently available or under development. Biomolecules having an appealing binding specificity linked to a certain ligand are included in biosensors. Through these exchanges, physical parameters (like conformation, enthalpy, mass, etc.) are altered, but they are limited to digital signal formation that is directly correlated with the efficacy of interactions. This process identifies and selects a capable biopharmaceutical manufacturing fragment and introduces recombinant DNA into a cell line that is appropriate for application. However, in many samples, the protein concentrations (low range of $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) are significantly lower than the costly current methods. Subsequently, the screening procedure gives preference to samples with high efficiency, seldom taking the product feature into account. Biosensors are one way to accomplish this.

CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC APPLICATION

The widespread usage of biosensors in numerous fields is one of the most significant applications in the field of medical diagnostics. Medical biochemistry labs no longer use the electrochemical capacity to measure lactic acid and glucose levels. Patients' self-testing, especially their self-monitoring of blood components, is another important area of clinical medicine and healthcare that commercial biosensors impede. Reusable biosensors currently provide for standardization and quality control, in contrast to disposable sticks that only allow for one measurement. By replacing the labor-intensive and historically slow testing with these analyses, patient care will become more effective. Biosensors will enable quick clinical decision-making by bringing clinical medicine closer to the patient's bedside.

FLUORESCENT BIOSENSORS

Fluorescent biosensors are imaging samples that are utilized in the research and development of cancer and pharmaceuticals. Researchers now know more about the function of cells and how biosensors teach enzymes. Genetically encoded FRET biosensors and FRET GFP-dependent biosensors play a significant role. Fluorescent bio-sensors are tiny platforms that are chemically, genetically, or enzymatically coupled to one or more fluorescent samples via a receptor. The receiver pinpoints particular studies or goals that are capable of quickly identifying and managing the transmission of a fluorescent signal. The presence, mobility, or condition of ions, protein biomarkers, and metabolites in the composite solution can all be precisely tested and reported using fluorescent biosensors on subjects (serum, cell extracts, etc.). Fluorescence is used in fields like signal transduction, apoptosis transcription, and the cell cycle.

WEARABLE BIOSENSORS FOR MONITORING WELL-BEING

Health monitoring also makes extensive use of wearable biosensors. Sensing devices are wireless electrodes wrapped in pads, bandages, or body-worn devices. The information gathered by biosensors is analyzed and utilized to track the results of essential clinical treatments and forecast when a patient's health will worsen. Analyses of biological agents, such as blood and sweat, are frequently employed to attain desired health results. For continuous glucose monitoring, the Fraunhofer Institute in Germany has created a portable, non-invasive nano-biosensor. The wearable device measures the amount of glucose in bodily fluids including perspiration and tears. This non-invasive glucose control system is still under development and is anticipated to be the future standard for wearable technology.

Figure 4 *Wearable Biosensor.*

MICROBIOLOGICAL BIOSENSORS

A microbial biosensor is an analytical device that uses a transducer and microorganisms to improve the speed, accuracy, and responsiveness of target analytes in a variety of applications, including food processing, safety, medicine, environmental monitoring, and protection. Previous microbial biosensors used the respiratory and metabolic activities of microorganisms to recognize a substance that is a substrate or inhibitor to these processes. In order to evaluate toxicity and bioavailability, genetically modified microorganisms based on the fusion of the lux, GFP, and lac Z gene reporters to an inducible gene promoter have become popular.

ABBREVIATIONS

- SPR** : Surface plasmon resonance;
- GFP** : Green fluorescent protein;
- AFP** : Auto fluorescent protein;
- BIA** : Biomolecular interface analysis;
- EWS** : Eva scent wave;
- SPW** : Surface plasmon wave;
- SPR** : Surface plasmine resonance;
- ESW** : Eva scent welle;
- GFP** : Green fluorescent protein;
- FRET** : Fluorescent protein.

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